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Academic Interest As Correlate Of Academic Engagament Among Undergraduate Students In Public Universities In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined academic interest as a correlate of academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design, involving a sample of 705 first-year undergraduates drawn through a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using the Academic Interest Scale and the Level of Students' Engagement Scale, both of which demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = 0.92$ and 0.83 , respectively). Analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation revealed a moderate positive relationship between academic interest and academic engagement ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.05$), with similar patterns observed for male ($r = 0.63$, $p < 0.05$) and female ($r = 0.59$, $p < 0.05$) students. These findings indicate that students with higher academic interest are more likely to be actively involved, motivated, and committed to learning activities. The study concludes that fostering academic interest is essential for enhancing engagement, and recommends strategies such as peer-assisted learning and inclusive learning environments to support student motivation and participation.

Keywords: Academic Engagement, Academic Interest, Gender, Public Universities, Undergraduate Students,

INTRODUCTION

Academic engagement has been widely examined in educational research as a crucial determinant of students' academic success, motivation, and overall well-being. It refers to the active and constructive participation of students in the learning process, reflecting their commitment, effort, and emotional investment in academic activities (Hernández & García, 2024). Engaged students are more likely to achieve better learning outcomes, demonstrate persistence, and experience greater satisfaction with their studies (Wang et al., 2022). However, poor academic engagement among undergraduates, particularly in public universities in Anambra State, remains a growing concern. Many students exhibit low motivation, lack of enthusiasm, minimal participation in class activities, and poor commitment to academic tasks (Okeke, 2020; Hidi & Renninger, 2020).

Academic engagement is closely associated with academic interest, which represents a student's intrinsic motivation and curiosity towards learning (Renninger & Hidi, 2016). Academic interest refers to a student's personal and intrinsic motivation to learn, characterized by a genuine curiosity and enthusiasm

for a subject or field of study (Renninger & Hidi, 2016). Academic interest plays a crucial role in fostering academic engagement, with students who exhibit high levels of interest in a subject more likely to engage in deep learning strategies, persist longer in tasks, and demonstrate greater overall motivation (Asanre et al., 2024). In the Nigerian context, Bautista et al. (2023) found that students' motivation to study, driven by academic interest, significantly predicted academic achievement. Academic interest has been linked to the development of expertise and long-term learning outcomes. Students who cultivate a strong interest in a subject are more likely to pursue it as a career or engage in lifelong learning (Renninger & Hidi, 2016). Academic interest, as an independent variable, plays a vital role in promoting academic engagement, achievement, and long-term learning outcomes. Academic interest may also be affected by gender.

Gender differences further shape academic engagement, with male students generally showing greater interest in STEM disciplines, while female students tend to prefer humanities and social sciences (Lei et al., 2018). These differences influence motivation, study habits, and participation in learning activities. Cultural expectations and socialisation patterns also affect how male and female students approach academic goals and interact with their studies (Wentzel, 2017). This study examines academic interest as correlate of academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State, aiming to provide insights that can guide strategies to enhance motivation, participation, and overall learning outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Academic engagement is a fundamental determinant of students' learning outcomes, motivation, and overall development in higher education. In public universities in Anambra State, Nigeria, there is growing concern over the poor academic engagement of undergraduate students. Many students exhibit low commitment to their studies, reflected in irregular attendance, minimal participation in class discussions, incomplete assignments, and a general lack of dedication to learning activities. Such disengagement undermines the purpose of tertiary education, which is to equip students with knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for personal, professional, and societal advancement.

A significant factor contributing to this trend is the declining level of academic interest among students. Many undergraduates appear increasingly preoccupied with the pursuit of sudden wealth, material possessions, and monetary pleasures rather than focusing on their studies. This shift in priorities has led to a decline in intrinsic motivation, with students showing more enthusiasm for short-term financial gains than for the sustained effort required for academic success. Consequently, engagement in meaningful learning activities is compromised, resulting in poor academic performance, reduced persistence in studies, and low levels of intellectual development.

The situation is further exacerbated by the societal emphasis on quick financial rewards, which encourages students to invest time and energy in non-academic ventures at the expense of their educational responsibilities. Despite the critical role of academic interest in fostering sustained engagement, many students in public universities in Anambra State lack the curiosity, focus, and commitment necessary to fully participate in the learning process. This problem highlights the urgent need to examine the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement, to identify strategies that can rekindle students' motivation, enhance their dedication to learning, and improve overall educational outcomes.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement of male and female undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design. The design was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to examine existing relationships among the variables without manipulation. The study was conducted in Anambra State, located in the southeast region of Nigeria, known for its rich cultural heritage and high literacy rate. The state hosts several higher institutions, including Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Uli and Igbariam Campus.

The population of the study comprised 14,101 first-year undergraduate students (6,854 males and 7,247 females) in public universities in Anambra State during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample of 705 students (343 males and 362 females) was drawn through a multi-stage sampling procedure involving proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Data were collected using two standardized and adapted instruments: Academic Interest Scale (AIS) developed by Jihyun Lee and Tracy Durkson (2018) and the Level of Students' Engagement Scale (Delfino, 2019). The instruments were validated by experts in educational foundations and construct validity was established through Principal Component Analysis (KMO = 0.835, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, $\chi^2(94) = 195.599$, $p < .000$). Reliability was determined using Cronbach Alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.92 and 0.83 for the respective instruments, indicating very high internal consistency.

Data collection was conducted by the researcher with assistance from four trained research assistants. Questionnaires were distributed and retrieved from respondents in their lecture halls, with a 97.7% return rate. Data were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Pearson correlation was used to answer research questions and test hypotheses on the relationships among variables at a 0.05 level of significance. Decisions on hypotheses were based on p-values, with significance established when $p \leq 0.05$.

Result

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state.

		academic interest	Academic Engagement	Remark
Academic interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.66**	
	N	684	684	Moderate positive relationship
academic engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.66**	1	

** . Correlation is significant at 0.05level(2-tailed).

Table 1 presented an analysis showing that there exists a moderate positive relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in

Anambra state. This deduction comes as a result of the 'r' having a positive value, $r = 0.66^{**}$ and $n = 684$. Hence, the study concluded that there exists a moderate positive relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female students in public universities in Anambra state?*

Table 2: Summary of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female students in public universities in Anambra state.

Correlations			Academic Interest	Academic Engagement	Remark
Male	Academic Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.63*	Moderate positive relationship
		N	319	319	
Female	Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.63*	1	Moderate positive relationship
	Academic Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.59**	
		N	265	265	
	Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.59**	1	

*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 presented an analysis showing that there exists a moderate positive relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female students in public universities in Anambra state. This deduction comes as a result of the 'r' having a positive value, $r = 0.63^{**}$, $n = 319$ and $r = 0.59^{**}$, $n = 265$ for males and females respectively. Hence, the study concluded that there exist a moderate positive relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female students in public universities in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: There was no significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State.

Correlations		Academic Interest	Academic Engagement	Decision
Academic Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.66**	Significant
	Sig.(2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	684	684	
Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.66**	1	Significant
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	684	684	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 3 above showed a significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state with $r = 0.66^{**}$ $n = 684$ and p -value =

0.00. Since p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis and do not reject the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state.

Hypothesis 2: There was no significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in public universities.

Correlations			Academic Interest	Academic Engagement	Remark
Male	Academic Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.63*	Significant
		Sig.(2-tailed)		0.02	
Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.63*	1		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.02			
Female	Academic Interest	Pearson Correlation	1	0.59**	Significant
		Sig.(2-tailed)		0.00	
Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.59**	1		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.00			
		N	319	319	
		N	265	265	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 8 above showed a significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in Anambra State with $r = 0.63^*$ $n = 319$, $P\text{-Value} = 0.02$ and $r = 0.59^{**}$ $n = 265$, $p\text{-value} = 0.00$ for males and females respectively. Since the p-value 0.02 and 0.00 are less than 0.05 for males and females, the study rejects the null hypothesis and do not reject the alternative hypothesis that there was a significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in Anambra State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The findings also showed that there existed a moderate positive and significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state. The findings of this study was in line with that of Asanre et al., (2024) who investigated the influence of interest and motivation on mathematics achievement among junior secondary school students in Ijebu Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria. The findings of this study was consistent with that of Uyun et al. (2022) who found a significant positive relationship between interest in academic activities participation ($r=0.516$; (<0.01)). As well, this study findings was in accordance with that of Hui et al. (2019) who found a positive correlation between situational interest and engaged learning .This finding was as a result of the respondents opinion on academic interest questionnaire, indicating that students who reported higher levels of academic interest also tended to exhibit higher levels of academic engagement..

The findings of the study showed that there existed a moderate positive and significant relationship between academic interest and academic engagement among male and female undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra state. The findings of this study however were at variance with that of

Bautista et al. (2023) that found that no significant differences were observed concerning individual interest and school engagement between the sexes. Additionally, a positive and significant relationship was observed between individual interest and school engagement. The findings of this study however disagrees with that of Yu et al. (2021) that found that BCH method was used to test the cross-sectional associations between gender role profiles and academic performance, while a manual BCH was performed to examine longitudinal associations, accounting for prior achievement. Latent profile analysis identified seven groups of adolescents (resister boys, cool guys, tough guys, relational girls, modern girls, tomboys, wild girls) and revealed the prevalence of each profile. Within-gender variations show that two thirds of the boys were motivated, engaged, and performed well in school. In contrast, half of the girls showed maladaptive patterns of motivation, engagement, and achievement, and could be considered academically at risk. By shifting the focus from "boys versus girls" to "which boys and which girls", this study reveals the invisibility of well-performing boys and underachieving girls in educational gender gap research. This finding was because of the responses of students to an academic interest questionnaire, indicating that students who reported higher levels of academic interest also tended to exhibit higher levels of academic engagement, with similar patterns observed among both male and female students

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that academic interest is a significant predictor of academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State. Students who demonstrate a strong interest in their studies are more likely to be motivated, dedicated, and actively involved in learning activities. This positive relationship holds for both male and female students, indicating that academic interest consistently drives engagement across genders. It is therefore imperative that measures are put in place to improve undergraduate students' academic interest in universities in Anambra State in particular and Nigeria in general.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made from the findings of this study

1. Educators should use peer-assisted learning strategies by incorporating peer-to-peer learning activities such as peer tutoring, peer review and peer feedback to enhance academic engagement.
2. Educators should create an inclusive learning environment that motivate students academic interest and fosters sense of engagement.

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